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Studies on Azido Complexes of Cobalt :

Part I

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ONLY a few transition metal ions are known to form azido complexes. It is only with cobalt as the central metal atom do we have a variety of complexes of the type MA_3B^1 , $MA_2B_2^2$, $M(AA)_2B_2$ and $MA_3B_3^3$ where A is a unidentate group such as ammonia, AA is a bidentate group such as ethylenediamine⁴, 1, 10 orthophenanthroline⁵, 2, 2' bipyridyl⁶, acetylacetonate⁷, and B is the azido group.

Of the bidentate ligands notable exceptions are dimethylglyoxime and biguanide. The synthesis of azido complexes of cobalt with dimethylglyoxime has been reported recently⁸. In this communication we report the preparation and characterisation of the pair cis and trans diazido bis biguanide cobalt(III) azide.

Experimental

Trans $Co[(big\ H)_2(N_3)_2]N_3 \cdot H_2O$ was prepared by reacting a saturated solution of $trans[Co(big\ H)_2Cl_2]Cl^9$ with an excess of solid sodium azide in a water bath kept at 60°-80° for half an hour. The solution is cooled and kept in a refrigerator overnight when orange crystals separate out. The crystals are filtered, washed with rectified spirit; the product is then recrystallised from water and dried in air.

The starting material for the preparation of $cis[Co(big\ H)_2(N_3)_2]N_3 \cdot H_2O$ is $cis[Co(big\ H)_2(NH_2)_2]Cl_2$ which was prepared by the method of Dutta & Sircar¹⁰. The compound was suspended in water air was passed through it for several hours and warmed on a water bath at 60°-80° for about an hour, and then treated with excess of solid sodium azide for half an hour at 60°-80°. The resulting solution was left in refrigerator over night and filtered to collect the violet crystals. The crystals were washed with water and alcohol and recrystallised from water and then air dried.

Cobalt was determined by converting it to cobalt sulphate and weighing as anhydrous cobalt sulphate. Total nitrogen was estimated by Duma's Method. Labile azide which constitutes one-third of the total azide was estimated by precipitating as silver azide and weighing. Analytical data are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1
CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF THE COMPLEXES

Compound	Co	N	N ₃ ⁻
Trans $[Co(big\ H^+)_2(N_3)_2]N_3 \cdot H_2O$	14.54	65.69	10.37 % Calcd.
	14.10	64.80	9.80 % Found.
Cis $[Co(big\ H^+)_2(N_3)_2]N_3 \cdot H_2O$	14.54	65.69	10.37 % Calcd.
	14.00	66.00	10.57 % Found.

Results and Discussion

The visible and U. V spectra was determined in a Beckman Spectrophotometer Model D. U. In aqueous media the cis compound has two peaks at 296 nm ($\epsilon_M=316$) and 508 nm ($\epsilon_M=168$). The trans compound has also two bands at 350 nm ($\epsilon_M=208$) and at 482 nm ($\epsilon_M=208$). For both compounds there is no evidence of any splitting of the bands in the visible region.

The i.r. spectra were recorded in a Beckman I.R. 20 in KBR pellets.

The bending mode $\delta(N_3)$ and the asymmetric stretch of co-ordinated azides $\nu(N_3)$ as lie in the regions 626-677 cm^{-1} and 2037-2092 cm^{-1} respectively for azide cobaltamine complexes⁴. The symmetric $\nu(N_3) S$ stretch¹¹, when it is observed as in $MoCl_4(N_3)_2$, occurs in the region 1190-1260 cm^{-1} .

On the basis of these the following assignments if i.r. bands may be made and is given in Table 2 in which v.s (denotes very strong, S means strong) and m indicates medium.

The assignment of $\nu(N_3) S$ is doubtful as a band at 1255 (m) is also observed in $[Co(big\ H)_2OH \cdot H_2O] SO_4 \cdot 2.5 H_2O$.

TABLE 2
INFRA-RED SPECTRA

	Trans	Cis
$\nu(N_2)$ as	2050 (v.s.)	2015 (v.s.)
$\nu(N_2)$ S	1245 (s)	1260 (s), 1285 (s)
$\delta(N_2)$	650 (m)	610 (m)

The vibration of lattice water are generally found in the region (3550-3200) cm^{-1} corresponding to the symmetric and antisymmetric O-H stretching modes^{1,2}. In both these azido complexes strong bands appear in these regions viz. 3200, 3300 and 3400 cm^{-1} for trans and a very broad strong absorption band from 3100 to 3400 cm^{-1} for the cis. An absorption at 1670 (S) for trans and 1680 (S) for cis may be assigned to H-O-H bending mode^{1,2}.

The azide outside the co-ordinating sphere for both these compounds was precipitated with silver nitrate, the filtrate acidified with perchloric acid, and then irradiated. It is found that in contrast to azido complexes containing ammonia and ethylenediamine, these biguanide complexes are rather inert to irradiation with visible light in perchloric acid medium and undergo decomposition on prolonged irradiation with ultra-violet light (365 nm). The details of this photodecomposition are under investigation.

Acknowledgement

We thank Dr. T. N. Chakravarti for the micro-analysis, Sri A. K. Chatterjee for the I. R. data and the U. G. C. for grants in support of this work.

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Titrimetric Determination of Lead(II), Molybdate and Phosphate using Pyridinol-Azo-Dyes as Visual Indicators

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Manuscript received 13 September 1976, revised 13 June 1977,
accepted 3 October 1977

IN the present study pyridinol azo dyes 1-(2,3-dihydroxy-4-pyridylazo)-4-benzene sulphonic acid (DHP-4S) and 1-(5-chloro-4-pyridylazo-2,3-diol)-4-benzene sulphonic acid (CPD-4S) have been successfully used as indicators for the titrimetric determination of lead (II)(complexometrically) and molybdate, phosphate (volumetrically). Earlier, formation of these dyes have been used as a sensitive test for the detection and determination of nitrite¹. The dyes have also been utilised for the complexometric determination of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II)².

Experimental

Reagents

Standard lead(II), molybdate and phosphate solutions were prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of Analar $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Na}_2(\text{MoO}_4)$, $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and KH_2PO_4 respectively in double distilled water. 0.1% Dye solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water.

Recommended Procedure

Determination of Lead(II) : To a suitable aliquot containing 10.35-414.4 mg of lead(II) add 5 ml of $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}/\text{NH}_4\text{OH}$ buffer of suitable pH (Table 1) and 0.1-0.3 ml of 0.1% indicator solution (DHP-4S or CPD-4S). Dilute the solution to approximately 20 ml by adding doubly distilled water and titrate at room temperature (27°) against standard EDTA ($1 \times 10^{-1} M$) taken in a microburette till a sharp colour change (magenta or red to orange) is obtained (Table 1). A white precipitate formed during the titration disappears on shaking. Titrations in reverse order can also be performed but the buffer should be added a few millilitre before the end-point.